

October 31, 2019

Survey of Insect Pests on Pigeonpea (*Cajanus Cajan*(L.) Millsp.) In Relation to Its Stages of Growth in Makurdi, Benue State of Nigeria

Author's Details: Aku, A. A.¹ and Ukwela, E. U.²

¹Department of Biology, Kaduna State College of Education Gidan Waya

²Department of Crop and Environmental Protection, University of Agriculture, Makurdi.

Received Date: 11-July-2019

Accepted Date: 20-July-2019

Published Date: 31-Oct-2019

Abstract

A study was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm University of Agriculture Makurdi (Lat. 7° 41'N, Long.8° 37'E), to document insects species associated with pigeonpea, and their relative abundance in relation to crop phenology. A suction sampler (D-vac) and pitfall traps were used to collect insects, from three weeks after planting through to crop maturity infesting pigeonpea in twenty 5m x 5m plots. A total of ninety eight (98) species of insects were collected in both the D-vac and pitfall sampling. These consisted of 78 pests, 16 predators and 4 parasitoids in 10 orders and 39 families. Among the insect pests' species, *Chrotogomus senegalensis*, *Helopeltis schoutedemi* and *Clavigralla tomentosicollis* were the most common pests. The action of these insect pests suggested that it is necessary to assess their status and economic impact prior to widespread dissemination of pigeonpea production technology in the area.

Key words: Pigeonpea, Insect pests, Sampling.

Introduction

Pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp.) is an important grain legume in many parts of the tropical regions of the world. It is highly tolerant to drought making it appropriate for production particularly in semi-arid regions of the world (Ritchie *et al.*, 2000; Silim *et al.*, 2005; Gwata and Siambi, 2009; Kumar *et al.*, 2011). In the African cropping systems, pigeonpea is grown mainly by smallholder farmers who derive multiple benefits inclusive of enhancement of soil fertility, increased availability of phytoproteins for human and livestock consumption and income generation (Amarteifio *et al.*, 2002; Shiferaw *et al.*, 2007; Egbe and Vange, 2008; Gwata, 2010).

In many pigeonpea production regions, the crop is constrained by biotic factors such as fungal diseases and insect pests (Okeyo-Owour and Khamala, 1980; Shanower *et al.*, 1999; Minja *et al.*, 1999; Hillock *et al.*, 2000; Gwata *et al.*, 2006; Dialoke *et al.*, 2010). The insects which attack the crop at the reproductive stage, feeding on the flowers and pods, thereby reducing the grain yield are a major constraint (Minja *et al.*, 1996; Shanower *et al.*, 1999; Srilaxmi and Ravindra, 2010; Dialoke *et al.* 2012; Marimuthu *et al.* 2012). For example pod sucking bugs mainly from the families Alydidae, Coreidae and Pentatomidae, have been reported to cause 50% to 75% damage (Materu, 1970; Minja, 1997) while pod feeding Lepidoptera, and seed feeding Diptera accounted for up to 35% and 46% yield losses, respectively, in Kenya (Minja, 1997).

Dialoke *et al.* (2012) assessed the relative abundance of pest species on early maturing pigeonpea cultivar planted at three different dates in Imo state. The result showed that *Zonocerus variegatus* L., *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner., *Riptortus dentipes* Fab., *Nezera viridula* L., *Clavigralla tomentosicollis* Stal. *Anoplocnemis curvipes* Fab., *Mylabris pustulata* Thunb., *Aphis crassivora* Koch. and *Megalurothrips sjostedti* Trybon. In an earlier publication following a survey of pigeonpea farms in Imo, Abia, Enugu, Anambra, Delta, Kogi and Benue state, Dialoke *et al.* (2010) observed the incidence of *Maruca*, *E. zenkinella*, ants, foliage beetles and termites. Information on the insect fauna of pigeon pea and their impact in Benue state is scanty. As pointed out by Odeny (2007), Kunjeku and Gwata (2011), it is necessary to understand insect activity in a crop before deciding on cost effective and environmentally sound pest management approaches. This experiment was designed to study the insect species and their relative abundance, in relation to pigeon pea growth stages.

Materials and Methods

October 31, 2019

The experiment was conducted during the rainy seasons of 2011 and 2012 at the Teaching and Research Farm of University of Agriculture, Makurdi, (Lat. 7° 41'N, Long. 8° 37'E). The land was ploughed, harrowed and ridged before planting. Seeds of Igbongbo white variety of pigeonpea were sown on 18th and 15th June, 2011 and 2012, respectively at a spacing of 30cm within and 100cm between rows in 20 plots each measuring 5m long by 5m wide. One metre inter space separated adjacent plots. The seedlings were thinned to one stand a week after planting. Weeds were controlled manually at 3, 6 and 9 weeks after planting (WAP).

All plots received a basal application of fertilizer 15kg N, 6.45kg P and 12.45kg K per hectare supplied as 100kg of NPK 15:15:15, 3 WAP.

Arthropods Sampling

Sampling with D-vac:

A suction sampler with 10cm inlet cone diameter was used to sweep the top and the sides of plants along the 5m length of a randomly selected row in each plot. Collections were made once a week between 1600 and 1800 hours. From 3 WAP to harvest, the arthropods collected were killed in ethyl acetate and preserved in 70% ethanol. Immature stages of arthropods which could be visually identified were preserved in ethanol. Butterflies and moths were pinned, dried using insect drying board and mounted in insect boxes. All insects collected were taken to insect museum centre at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for identification.

Pitfall trapping

A pitfall trap was set up in the centre row of each plot. A hole was made on top of the ridge in the centre of the plot and a trap cup containing 50ml of 5% formalin was inserted. Few drops of kerosene were added to the formalin to reduce evaporation. A tripod stand covered with polythene was placed on top of the trap cup in such a way that large animal could not go in. The traps were serviced and insects collected once a week from 3 WAP to harvest and the insect collected were dried, pinned and identified as described above.

Data Analysis

Relative abundance of each insect species was computed based on the total number of insects collected. For the three most abundant species, relationship of abundance with temperature, rainfall and relative humidity was investigated. Students't-test was used to compare D-vac and Pitfall collections in each of the two years. The infestation of some common insect pests in relation to the growth stages on pigeonpea was shown in a diagram. While the trend in the abundance of insects collected with D-vac and pitfall were graphically compared.

Results

The total number of insect species associated with pigeonpea using the two sampling methods (D-vac and pitfall trap) is shown in Table 1. The most abundant insect species caught were in the Order Coleoptera with 13 families. This was followed by collections in the Order Heteroptera. Collections in Odonata and Thysanoptera had only one family each. Table 2 show the total number of insects sampled in the two cropping seasons; the numbers collected in 2011 were significantly higher ($\alpha=0.05$) than 2012, irrespective of sampling methods.

Table 3 shows the abundant insect pest species caught with D-vac and pitfall trap over two cropping seasons (2011 and 2012). Seventy eight (78) species of insect pests were collected in both the D-vac and pitfall sampling in the two cropping seasons. The number of insect collected with D-vac was 3 times more than the number collected with pitfall trap (Table 3). Only four insect pests species were caught with both D-vac and pitfall trap. Out of the seventy eight (78) insect pests species collected, *Helopeltis shoutedemi*, *Chrotogomus senegalensis* and *C. tomentosicolis* were the most abundant.

At the vegetative stage, *Aphis*, *A. crassivora* was the dominant insect seen attacking the young stems or the leaf. Other defoliating species included *Z. variegatus*, *Monolepta* sp., the lady bird beetles, *Harmonia conformis* B. incidence of *H. conformis*, *H. schoutedemi*, *Z. variegatus* traversed vegetative to early reproductive stage whereas *C. senegalensis* was present through to crop maturity (Fig. 1).

The correlation between abundance of *H. schoutedemi*, *C. senegalensis* and *C. tomentosicolis* and some of the weather parameters for the two cropping seasons in table 4. Abundance of *H. schoutedemi* was not significantly correlated with all the weather parameters in the two cropping seasons except temperature in

October 31, 2019

2012. *C. senegalensis* was significantly correlated with rainfall and relative humidity in the two cropping seasons; whereas it was not significantly correlated to temperature in the two seasons. *C. tomentosicolis* was not significantly correlated with temperature in the two cropping seasons and relative humidity in 2012; whereas it was significantly correlated to rainfall in the two cropping seasons and relative humidity in 2011 cropping season.

The predominant predatory insects are shown in Table 5. Ants in the Family Formicidae dominated by *Pheidole* sp. were the prominent predators.

Table 6 show the relative abundance of parasitoid caught on pigeonpea farm for the two cropping seasons. *Iphiaulax* sp. was the most abundant species.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the trends in collection made with D-vac and Pitfall trap during crop growth in 2011 and 2012, respectively. Pitfall trap catches reached a peak in September in both years. D-vac collections peaked in November.

Discussion

The composition of phytophagous species were to a large extent similar to those reported from studies in Uganda and other parts of Nigeria (Night and Ogenga-Latigo, 1994; Minja *et al*, 1999; Dialoke *et al*, 2010; Kunjeku and Gwata, 2011) thereby confirming that a fairly common spectrum of insect pests occurs on the crop across the African sub- continent. The reproductive phase of pigeonpea attracted insect species such as *A. curvipes*, *C. tomentosicolis*, *M. pustulata*, *R. dentipes*, *M. tesulalis*, *M. obtusa*, that have been designated major pests on soybean and cowpea (Jakai and Raheja 1983; Ndam, 2007; Egbo, 2011). These insects cause damage in such a way that mature seeds turn black and shrivelled rendering them unacceptable for human consumption, and not suitable for planting (Materu, 1970).

In this study, 78 species of insect pests were collected; elsewhere, Kochler and Singh (1983) reported 38 species of insect pests on pigeonpea at Hisar in India. Srilaxmi and Ravindra (2010) reported 18 species in six Orders and sixteen families of insect pests on pigeonpea in Gulbarka, Karnataka. Out of these Orders, members of Lepidoptera caused maximum damage followed by coleoptera, diptera, hemiptera and homoptera. Marimuthu *et al*. (2012) reported 20 species of insect pests of pigeonpea and 5 species of predatory insects in Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. Kunjeku and Gwata (2011) in South Africa reported 15 species of insect pests on 19 exotic medium duration pigeonpea cultivars. In Nigeria, Madang *et al*. (2012) reported 8 species of insect pests of pigeonpea grown under ratoon and in mixture with maize at Nsukka. Dialoke *et al*. (2010) reported the extent of borer damage to pigeonpea on their survey of insect pests of pigeonpea in some parts of Nigeria.

In contrast to the findings of Muthomi *et al.*, (2007), Srilaxma and Ravindra, (2010), Dialoke *et al* (2012) and Kunjeku and Gwata, (2011), species of *H. armigera* was not observed. In addition to the common insect pests species associated with pigeonpea documented by other authors, *H. schoutedemi* and *C. senegalensis* were also observed to be the most common in this study.

With D-vac sampling, insect abundance increase between October and December coinciding with the reproductive stage of the crop. Insect caught with the pitfall traps were high between September and November. This could probably coincide with abundance of food availability. The distribution of the common insect species on the growth stages in Fig. 4 was also probably due to favourable environmental conditions and food availability.

The population of the insect pests of pigeonpea was higher in 2011 than in 2012. This finding is in agreement of Srilaxma and Ravindra (2010) who reported that the population fluctuation and densities of insect pest species, influx of pests in the field and their succession at various growth stages of pigeonpea crop differs from region to region and from season to season due to prevailing local micro- and macro-climatic conditions.

The highly disproportionate values of phytophagous to predators/parasitic species might be due to interaction between food availability and abundance of natural resources as reported by Duffield, (1995). These high disproportionate values of phytophagous to predators/parasitic species caution against indiscriminate usage of synthetic insecticide. Where insecticides have to be used for effective control of major phytophagous insect, selection criteria should necessarily include impact on non-target organisms (Muthomi *et al.*, 2007).

References

- i. Amarteifio, J.O., Munthali, D.C., Karikari, S.K. and Morake, T. K. (2002). *The composition of pigeonpea (Cajanus cajan (L.) Millsp.) grown in Botswana. Plant Foods Human Nutr.* 57:173-177.
- ii. Dialoke, S.A., Agu, C.M., Ojioko, F.O., Onweremadu, E., Onyishi, G.O., Ozor, B.C., Ofor, M.O., Ibeachwuchi, H., Chigbundu, I. N., Ngwata, A. A. and Ugwoke, F.O. (2010). *Survey of insect pests of pigeonpea in Nigeria. Journal of Sustainable Agricultural Research* 8:1-8
- iii. Dialoke, S.A., Emosairue, S.O., Egbo, E.O., Tobith, F.O. and Akalaza, J.N. (2012). *The major insect pests species and their relative abundance on early maturing pigeonpea (Cajanus cajan (L.) Millsp.), in Agro-Ecological zone of Imo state, Nigeria. Paper presented on the 43rd Annual conference of Entomological Society of Nigeria at University of Benin Edo State, Nigeria.*
- iv. Duffield, S. J (1995). *Crop-specific difference in the seasonal abundance of four major predatory groups on sorghum and short duration pigeonpea. International Conference on pigeonpea Newsletter* 2:74-75
- v. Egbe, O.M. and Vange, T. (2008). *Yield and agronomic characteristics of 29 pigeonpea genotypes at Otobi in southern Guinea savanna of Nigeria. Nature and Science* 6(2):39-50.
- vi. Faris, D. G., Saxena, K.B., Mazumdar, S. and Singh, U. (1987). *Vegetable pigeonpea: A promising crop for India. ICRISAT, Patanncheru, India. Pp. 1-13.*
- vii. Gwata, E. T. (2010). *Potential impact of edible tropical legumes on crop productivity in the small-holder sector in Sub-Sahara Africa. J. Food Agric. Environ.* 8:4413-4417.
- viii. Gwata, E.T. and Siambi, M. (2009). *Genetic enhancement of pigeonpea for high latitude areas in southern Africa. Afr. J. Biotech.* 8:4413-4417.
- ix. Gwata, E.T., Silim, S.N. and Mgonja, M. (2006). *Impact of a new source of resistance to fusarium wilt in pigeonpea. J. Phytopathol.* 154:62-64.
- x. Hillock, R.J., Minja, E., Mwage, A., Silim, N.M. and Subrahmanyam, P. (2000). *Diseases and pests of pigeonpea in eastern Africa: A Review. International Journal of Pest Management.* 46(1):7-18.
- xi. Jakai, L. E. N. and Raheja, A. K. (1983). *Soybean entomology: insect survey and yield loss assessment. In : Internatioal Istitute of Tropical Agriculture Annual Report for 1983, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, p.101*
- xii. Kochler, C.S. and Rachie, K.O. (1971). *Notes on the control and biology of Helicoverpa armigera (Hubner.) in pigeonpea in Uganda. East African Agriculture and Forestry Journal* 36(3):296-297.
- xiii. Kochler, K.S. and Singh, Z. (1983). *Insect pests associated with pigeon. International Pigeonpea News Letters.* 2:43-44.
- xiv. Kumar, R.R., Karjoi, K. and Naik, G.R. (2011). *Variation of sensitivity to drought stress in pigeonpea (Cajanus cajan (L.) Millsp.) during seed germination and early seedling growth. World J. Sci. Technol.* 1:11-18.
- xv. Kunjeku, E.C. and Gwata, E.T. (2011). *A preliminary survey of insect species occurring at the reproductive stage in pigeonpea grown in Limpopo (South Africa). Journal of Food Agriculture and Environment* 9(3&4):988-991.
- xvi. Marimuthu, R., Siva, K. and Anto, C. (2012). *A survey of insect pests of pigeonpea and their predators in Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. International Journal of Agricultural Science* 2(1):090-093.
- xvii. Minja, E.M. (1997). *Insects of pigeonpea in Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda and grain yield losses in Kenya. A consultants report ICRISAT, Bulawayo, Zimbabwe. P 65.*
- xviii. Minja, E.M. (2001). *Yield losses due to field pests and integrated pest management strategies for pigeonpea: A synthesis. In: Proc. Region. Workshop on status and potential of pigeonpea in Eastern and Southern Africa, 2000, Nairobi, Kenya. Pp 48-54.*
- xix. Minja, E.M., Shanower, T.G., Songa, J.M., Ong'aro, J.M., Kawonga, W.T., Mviha, F.A., Slumpa, S., Okurut-Akol, H. and Opiyo, C. (1999). *Surveys of insect pest damage and pest management practices on pigeonpea in farmer's fields in Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda. African Crop Science Journal* 7(1):59-69.

October 31, 2019

- xx. Minja, E.M., Shanower, T.G., Songa, J.M., Ongaro, J.M., Mviha, P., Myaka, F.A. and Okurut-Akol, H. (1996). Pigeonpea seed damage from insect pests in farmers fields in Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda. *Int. chickpea and pigeonpea Newsl.* 3:97-98.
- xxi. Muteru, M.E.A. (1970). Damage caused by *Acanthomia tomentosicollis* Stal and *A. horrida* Germar (Hemiptera: Coreidae). *East African Agricultural and Forestry Journal* 35:429-435.
- xxii. Muthomi, J.W., Otieno, P.E., Cheminingwaan and Nderitu, J.H. (2007). Effect of chemical spray on pests and yield of food grain legumes. *Afric. Crop Sci. J.* 8:981-986.
- xxiii. Night, G. and Ogenga-Latigo, M.W.(1993). Relative infestation and damage of some pigeonpea cultivars by lepidopteran pod borer in Uganda. *African Crop Science Journal.* 1(2):117-122.
- xxiv. Odeny, D.A. (2007). The potential of pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.)Millsp.) in Africa. *Nat. Resour. For.* 3:297-305.
- xxv. Okeyo-Owuor, J.B. and Kamala, C.P.M.(1980). Insect pod borers of pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan*(L.) Millsp) and their influence on developing pods and final seed yield in Kenya. *Kenya Journal of Science and Technology.* 1, 79-86.
- xxvi. Ritchie, J.M., Abeyasekero, S., Chanika, S., Ross, C.S.M., Mkandawire, S.J., Maulana, C.B.K., Shaba, T.H. and Milanzi, T.T.K.(2000). Assessment of improved pigeonpea varieties under smallholder management. In: Richie, J.M.(ed). *Integrated crop management research in Malawi: Developing technology with farmers.* Chatnam, U.K. Pp 29-35.
- xxvii. Shanower, T. G., Romeis, J.and Minja, E. M. (1999). Insect pest of pigeon pea and their management. *Annual Review of Entomology* Vol. 44: 77 – 96.
- xxviii. Shiferaw, B., Silim, S., Muricho, G., Audi, J., Lyimo, S., You, L. and Christiansen, J.L.(2007). Assessment of the adoption and impact of improved pigeonpea varieties in Tanzania. *Journal of sustainable Agric. Res.* 5:1-27.
- xxix. Silim, S.M., Bramel, P.J., Akonay, H.B., Mligo, J.K. and Christiansen, J. L. (2005). Cropping systems, uses and primary in situ characterization of Tanzania pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.)Millsp.) landraces. *Gen. Res. Crop Evol.* 52:645-654.
- xxx. Srilaxmi, K. and Ravindra, P. (2010). Diversity of insect pests of pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp.) and their succession in relation to crop phenology in Gulbarga, Karnaka. *An international Journal of Environmental Science.* 4(4): 273-276.

Table 1: Families of insects associated with pigeonpea in 2011 and 2012 cropping seasons.

Order	Family	D-vac	Pitfall	Total
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	60	28	88
	Chrysomelidae	54	22	76
	Elasteridae	28	-	28
	Cincinellidae	5	-	5
	Curculionidae	51	94	145
	Anobiidae	3	-	3
	Tenebrionidae	-	92	92
	Carabidae	29	14	43
	Buprestidae	66	-	66
	Anthidae	40	12	52
	Scarabidae	5	12	17
	Staphylinidae	-	7	7
	Scarabaedae	25	-	25
	Heteroptera	Miridae	216	-
Coreidae		245	-	245
Plataspidae		25	19	44
Pentatomidae		20	-	20
Aphrophoridae		8	-	8
Pyrrhociridae		13	-	13
Lygaeidae		15	26	41
Reduviidae		27	17	44
Orthoptera	Pyrgomorphidae	212	-	212
	Gryllidae	16	56	72
	Tettiginiidae	5	-	5
	Acrididae	23	13	36
Diptera	Tephritidae	5	-	5
	Therevidae	20	-	20
	Agromylidae	62	-	62
	Seenopidae	9	-	9
Dictyoptera	Blattidae	5	-	5
	Mantidae	7	13	20
Lepidoptera	Pterophoridae	8	-	8
	Crambidae	10	-	10
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	195	392	587
	Vespidae	3	-	3
	Braconidae	4	18	22
	Eurytomidae	-	24	24
Homoptera	Alydidae	60	-	60
	Petatomidae	17	-	17
	Aphididae	13	-	13
	Cicadellidae	94	-	94
Thysanoptera	Tripidae	46	-	46
Odonata	Libellulidae	6	-	6
Total		2976	722	3698

October 31, 2019

Table 2: Comparison of insect collection from pigeonpea using D-vac and pitfall trap at Makurdi in 2011 and 2012.

Plots	D-Vac		Pitfall	
	2011	2012	2011	2012
1	36	39	23	15
2	54	30	30	25
3	24	34	17	10
4	58	36	23	29
5	55	53	11	25
6	53	43	33	28
7	20	41	29	15
8	38	45	17	34
9	30	33	35	19
10	54	34	16	10
11	59	20	29	14
12	53	36	18	20
13	45	18	16	15
14	57	23	38	12
15	33	28	16	21
16	53	35	23	17
17	31	25	20	12
18	54	38	19	15
19	53	39	20	22
20	59	34	23	16
X	57.95	35.7	44.3	34.7
S.E	1.99	1.96	2.21	1.58
$t_{0.05}$	1.99*		3.49*	

* Significant at 0.05% level of probability.

October 31, 2019

Table 3: Composition and relative abundance (%) of insect pests associated with pigeonpea over two cropping seasons (2011 and 2012) in Makurdi, Benue state.

Order	Family	Species	Relative abundance (%)		
			D-vac ^a	Pitfall ^b	Combined sampling.
Heteroptera	Miridae	<i>Helopeltis schoutedemi</i> (Reut.)	15.5		11.9
Orthoptera	Pyrgomorphidae	<i>Chrotogomus senegalensis</i> (Krauss.)	14.3	–	11.0
Heteroptera	Coreidae	<i>Clavigralla tomentosicolis</i> (Stal.)	22.1	–	16.9
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Exochonus flavipes</i> (Thunb.)	9.4	–	4.2
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Pagria suturalis</i> (Lef.)	0.9	–	0.4
Coleoptera	Elasteridae	<i>Heteroderes</i> SP.	0.6	–	0.2
Heteroptera	Platespidae	<i>Coptosoma</i> Sp.	0.5	–	0.1
Diptera	Therevidae	<i>Caenophano myianuba</i> (Wied.)	1.4	–	0.7
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Siderodactylus Sagittarius</i> (Ov.)	1.7	–	0.9
Orthoptera	Pyrgomorphidae	<i>Maura acutipennis</i> (Guer.)	1.7	–	0.9
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Cheilomenes sulphurea</i> (Oliv.)	0.8	–	0.3
Heteroptera	Pentatomidae	<i>Menida</i> sp.	1.8	–	0.9
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Mesoplatys cinta</i> (Oliv.)	5.1.	–	1.5
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Monotepta</i> sp.	1.2	–	0.4
Coleoptera	Anobiidae	<i>Cateroma</i> sp.	0.9	–	0.3
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Thaipophila</i> sp	–	1.1	0.6
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Platypria centetes</i> (Guer.)	–	1.5	0.5
Heteroptera	Aphrophoridae	<i>Poophilus costalis</i> (Walker.)	0.6	–	0.2
Heteroptera	Pyrrhociridae	<i>Dysdercus volkeri</i> (F.)	0.9	–	0.3
Heteroptera	Coreidae	<i>Anoplocnemis curvipes</i> (Fab.)	7.5	–	3.7
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Cryptocephales</i> sp.	0.6	–	0.2
Heteroptera	Pentatomidae	<i>Diploxysfissa</i> (Er.)	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Philopona fulvicollis</i> (Fab.)	0.9	–	0.3
Heteroptera	Lygaeidae	<i>Graptostet hussersus</i> (F.)	0.4	–	0.1
Dictyoptera	Blattidae	<i>Blattela</i> sp.	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Monoleota duplicata</i> (Sahlb.)	0.6	–	0.3
Heteroptera	Reduviidae	<i>Sphedanolestes picturellus</i> (Schout.)	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Platymetopus vestitus</i> (Dej.)	0.5	–	0.2

October 31, 2019

Lepidoptera	Pterophoridae	<i>Exelastis atomosa</i> (W.)	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Buprestidae	<i>Mylabris pustulata</i> (Thunb.)	4.5	–	1.5
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Cataglyphis bicolour</i> (Fab.)	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Platymetopus vestitus</i> (Dej.)	0.9	–	0.4
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Echinocnemus</i> sp.	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Epilachna similis</i> (Thumb.)	–	1.9	0.8
Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Pteronemobius massaicus</i> (Sjost.)	–	1.3	0.6
Heteroptera	Miridae	<i>Eurystylus</i> sp.	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Epilachna similis</i> (Thumb.)	0.4	–	0.1
Heteroptera	Lygaeidae	<i>Naphius zavatharri</i> (Mancini.)	0.4	–	0.1
Orthoptera	Tettigoniidae	<i>Amytta</i> sp.	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Podagrica sjostedti</i> (Jac.)	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Oetheca</i> sp.	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Siderodactylus Sagittarius</i> (Ov.)	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Padagrica uniforma</i> (Jac.)	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Harmonia conformis</i> (Far.)	0.4	–	0.1
Diptera	Tephritidae	<i>Didacus ciliates</i> (Leow.)	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Cincinellidae	<i>Cincindela senegalensis</i> (Dej.)	0.4	–	0.1
Heteroptera	Lygaeidae	<i>Graptostet husserrus</i> (F.)	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pycnodactylus</i> sp.	0.4	–	0.1
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Camponotus perrisi</i> (For.)	0.4	–	0.1
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Camponotus maculatus</i> (Fab.)	0.6	–	0.2
Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i> (Deg.)	1.1	3.3	1.7
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Copa occidentalis</i> (Weise.)	0.4	–	0.1
Heteroptera	Lygaeidae	<i>Naphiellus dilutes</i> (Harvath.)	–	2.2	1.1
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Menemachus</i> sp.	0.4	–	0.1
Heteroptera	Reduviidae	<i>Lisarda</i> sp.	0.6	–	0.2
Coleoptera	Scarabaeidae	<i>Trochalus verticilineatus</i> (Brok.)	0.4	–	0.1
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Gasterodissus staudingeri</i> (Petri.)	–	5.3	1.7
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Gonocephalum dermestiodes</i> (G.)	–	4.7	1.9
Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Catantopsan nulatus</i> (Uvarov.)	1.6	3.1	1.9
Heteroptera	Plataspidae	<i>Coptosoma stali</i> (Mont.)	0.8	2.0	1.1

October 31, 2019

Coleoptera	Anthiedae	<i>Formicomus</i> sp.	1.4	2.7	1.7
Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Scapsipedus marginatus</i> (Afz.)	–	7.5	3.2
Heteroptera	Lygaeidae	<i>Rhyparochromus littoralis</i> (Dist.)	–	3.3	1.3
Hemiptera	Formicidae	<i>Campenotus sericeus</i> (Fab.)	–	4.9	1.8
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Megacephala quadrisignata</i> (Daj.)	–	0.4	0.1
Coleoptera	Scarabidae	<i>Gymnopleurus</i> sp.	–	0.4	0.1
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Phrynocolus dentatus</i> (Sol.)	–	0.9	0.4
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Nematocerus</i> sp.	–	0.4	0.1
Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Acanthoplis tusacutus</i> (Sauss.)	–	1.5	0.7
Heteroptera	Lygaeidae	<i>Naphiellus dilutes</i> (Harvath.)	–	0.4	0.1
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Gasterodiscus staudingeri</i> (Petri.)	–	0.8	0.3
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Gonocephalum dermestiodes</i> (G.)	–	0.8	0.3
Diptera	Agromyzidae	<i>Melanagromyza obtuse</i>	4.2	–	2.1
Homoptera	Alydidae	<i>Riptortus dentipes</i> (Fabr.)	4.1	–	2.0
Homoptera	Petatomidae	<i>Nezera viridula</i> (L.)	5.2	–	3.1
Homoptera	Aphididae	<i>Aphis craccivora</i> (Scopoli.)	8.3	–	4.5
Homoptera	Cicadellidae	<i>Empoasca fabae</i> (K.)	6.4	–	3.6
Thysanoptera	Thripidae	<i>Helionothrips</i> sp	2.8	0.4	1.3
Total			1482	451	1934

a= Collected with D-vac sample from 4m- row of pigeonpea in 2011 and 2012 cropping seasons

b = Collected with Pitfall traps in pigeonpea in 2011 and 2012 cropping seasons.

October 31, 2019

Fig 1. Insect infestation in relation to pigeonpea growth stages.

Table 4: Correlation of some weather parameters with populations of *H. schoutedemi*, *C. senegalensis* and *C. tomentosicolis* in 2011 and 2012 pigeonpea cropping seasons.

Weather Parameters ^a	Year	<i>H.schoutedemi</i>	<i>C. senegalensis</i>	<i>C. tomentosicolis</i>
Rainfall	2011	-0.5 ^{ns}	0.3*	1.0*
	2012	-0.7 ^{ns}	0.5*	0.4*
Temperature	2011	0.1 ^{ns}	0.2 ^{ns}	-0.3 ^{ns}
	2012	0.2*	0.1 ^{ns}	-0.3 ^{ns}
Relative humidity	2011	-0.3 ^{ns}	0.5*	1.0*
	2012	-0.6 ^{ns}	0.8*	-0.4 ^{ns}

a= During crop growth period (June-January)

*= Significant at p=0.05 level of probability

ns= Not significant infestation in relation to pigeonpea growth stages.

October 31, 2019

Table 5: Composition and relative abundance (%) of predatory insects associated with pigeonpea over two cropping seasons (2011 and 2012) in Makurdi, Benue state.

Order	Family	Species	Relative abundance (%)		
			D-vac ^a	Pitfall ^b	Combined sampling.
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	66.0	87.2	82.1
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Stenodindodes</i> sp.	3.6	0.5	1.5
Heteroptera	Pentatomidae	<i>Andrallus spinnidens</i> (Fabr.)	4.2	–	1.1
Heteroptera	Reduviidae	<i>Rhynocoris fuscipes</i> (F.)	2.0	1.0	0.8
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Componotus sericeus</i> (Fab.)	2.0	0.3	0.8
Dictyoptera	Mantidae	<i>Mantis religiosa</i> (Couple.)	2.8	0.8	0.9
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Paederrus sabaeus</i> (Er.)	0.0	2.0	0.3
Hymenoptera	Vespidae	<i>Antodynerus bellatulus</i> (Sanss.)	1.2	–	0.1
Heteroptera	Reduviidae	<i>Tinnaber landi</i> (Villiers.)	–	0.8	0.3
Heteroptera	Reduviidae	<i>Rhinocoris corallipes</i> (Villiers.)	1.2	–	0.1
Heteroptera	Reduviidae	<i>Nagusta</i> sp.	2.4	–	0.8
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Megaponera foetens</i> (Fab.)	4.8	4.9	1.2
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> (Linn.)	1.2	–	0.1

October 31, 2019

Odonata	Libellulidae	<i>Brachythemis leucosticta</i> (Kirby.)	6.4	–	2.2
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Dorylus affinis</i> (Emy.)	–	4.3	1.8
Diptera	Seenopidae	<i>Scenoinus lucidus</i> (Beck.)	3.6	–	1.1
Total			250	391	738

a= Collected with D-Vac from 4m-row of pigeonpea.

b= Collected with Pitfall traps in pigeonpea.

October 31, 2019

Table 6: Composition and relative abundance (%) of parasitoids associated with pigeonpea over two cropping seasons (2011 and 2012) in Makurdi, Benue state.

Order	Family	Species	D-Vac ^a	Relative abundance (%)	
				Pitfall ^b	Combined
Hymenoptera	Braconidae	<i>Bracon hebetor</i> (Say)	9.6	34.6	26.2
Hymenoptera	Braconidae	<i>Brausia</i> sp	12.9	-	18.8
Hymenoptera	Braconidae	<i>Iphiaulax</i> sp	15.4	2.9	11.2
Hymenoptera	Eurytomidae	<i>Eurytoma</i> sp	-	19.2	10.7
Total no. caught			13	21	34

a=Collected with D-Vac from 4m-row of pigeonpea

b= Collected with pitfall traps in pigeonpea plots.

October 31, 2019

Fig.2: Monthly number of insects collected by D-Vac sampler and Pitfall trap in relation to pigeonpea growth in 2011.

Fig 3: Monthly number of insect collected by D-Vac and pitfall trap in relation to pigeon pea growth stages in 2012.

¹Corresponding author (akuayuba60@gmail.com).